

THE PLURAL MORPHEME *-TACHI* IN JAPANESE**Hagi A.**

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The purpose of this paper is to discuss the existence of plural morphemes in Japanese, a language where nouns are not marked for Gender or Number whatsoever. Nonetheless, there seems to be a restricted number of morphemes like *-tachi* or *-gata* which are adjoined lexically to a Noun Phrase in order to render it plural. As a matter of fact, I chose to analyze these morphemes with the sole purpose to understand whether they help convey numerosity in Japanese in a similar manner as the plural morpheme *-s* does in English. One important aspect of the problem is that we can further show that these two plural morphemes help convey definiteness in Japanese, since they bear with themselves a plus of semantic content, which otherwise it would be deemed non-existent.

Keywords: Pluralization, Japanese, Morphemes, *-tachi*, *-gata* Countability, Noun Phrases, Definiteness.

12.3.-Tachi the Equivalent of Plural Morphemes in Japanese?

Japanese is another example of a classifier language that has plural marking. In this language, the plural marker *-tachi* allows either a plural reading or an associative reading. However, the two readings are more freely available in Japanese than in Chinese or Korean for example. The relevant distribution of *-tachi* involves movement. This is taken as evidence to suggest that the different interpretations of *-tachi* occupy different positions, Num and D respectively (Ueda and Haraguchi 2008, Ochi 2008), unlike English *-s*, that is argued to occupy Num only to render the plural reading valid.

English *-s* allows only a plural reading with common nouns, and either a plural reading or an associative reading with proper nouns. In Japanese, however, both proper nouns and common nouns allow either a plural or an associative reading (Nakanishi and Tomioka 2004, Nakanishi and Ritter 2009). With a proper noun, *Hanako-tachi*, , can mean either ‘*Hanako and others*’ (associative) or ‘*a group of people all named Hanako*’ (plural). For common nouns, the usual reading is one of plurality; however, this is not necessarily the case (Nakanishi and Tomioka 2004). For example, *kodomo-tachi* ‘child-TACHI’ could denote a group that does not uniformly consist of children, but may include others who are associated with the children. This is shown most clearly with examples such as (14) (Nakanishi and Tomioka 2004:128):

1. Koen-de utat-tei-ta onnanoko-tachi-no
nakani-wa otokonoko-moni, san-nin mazatteita
N.park-at sing-PROG-PAST girl-TACHI-GEN
among-TOP boy-also a.few-CL were.included
‘Among (the) girls who were singing in the park,
a few boys were included.’

In order for (427) to be interpretable, it must be the case that *onnanoko-tachi* ‘girl-TACHI’ allows the possibility of individuals who are not girls in its denotation; thus, *-tachi* must allow an associative reading with plurals as well. Thus, *-tachi* has two available readings, like English *-s*, although the latter occupies Num on both readings. The two differ in that it is possible to have more than one *-tachi* morpheme suffixed to a noun, either proper or common, as in (2ab), while with

Chinese *-s* this is impossible: (Ueda Haraguchi 2008:237):

2. a. *gakusei-tachi-tachi*b. *Taroo-tachi-tachi**student-TACHI-TACHI**Taroo-TACHI-TACHI*

‘the students and their associates’

‘Taroo and his associates and their associates’

In (2), the two examples have slightly different readings: in (2a) the first *-tachi* has a plural reading and the second has an associative reading, while in (2b) both have associative readings. Ueda and Haraguchi note that these are the only possible interpretations of a double-*tachi* construction; it is impossible for them both to have plural readings, or to get an associative reading from the first and a plural reading from the second.

Assuming that multiple NumPs cannot occur, Ueda and Haraguchi propose that the plural *-tachi* is a Num head, which takes an NP complement, thus allowing no recursion. On the other hand, assuming that a DP can be recursive, it is proposed that *-tachi* as an associative morpheme is a D head that takes a DP complement, thus allowing either recursion of a second associative morpheme or the presence of a lower plural morpheme. Under this view, *-tachi* occupies different head positions:

3.

Given this structural analysis of *-tachi*, let us consider the co-occurrence of plural *-tachi* and classifiers. The plural marker *-tachi* can co-occur with classifier phrases (CLP) with common nouns, regardless of

whether the CLP precedes or follows the head noun (Ochi 2012:52). In other words, the plural marker is allowed in both the prenominal order where CLP precedes the head noun, in which case they are accompanied by *-no*, marking the phrase as a genitive modifier, and the postnominal order (4b) where CLP follows the head noun.

4. a. Boku wa san nin no gakusei tachi o maneita.
I TOP three CL GEN student TACHI ACC invited
 'I invited (the) three students for a meal.
 b. Boku wa gakusei tachi san nin o maneita.
I TOP student TACHI three CL ACC invited
 'I invited (the) three students for a meal.

In the prenominal order (4a), CLP has been proposed to be a modifier adjoined to NP (as argued for on the basis of N' ellipsis in Saito, Lin, and Murasugi 2006), which is widely assumed in the Japanese literature (e.g., Ueda and Haraguchi 2008, Huang and Ochi 2011, 2012, Ochi 2012). The adjunct analysis of a CLP will be illustrated later. Under this view, *-tachi* is the head of a higher NumP, and it is still adjacent to the head noun, which capture the word order shown in (5). That is, *-tachi* and a classifier occupy different head positions, and thus, the co-occurrence of classifiers and *-tachi* is fully expected.

5.

(adapted from Ueda and Haraguchi 2008: 235)

As for the postnominal order as in (4b), according to Tsuyago (2019) a modifier analysis of CLP along the lines of (5) must be rejected, since modifiers invariably precede the head noun in Japanese nominal phrases; Japanese is a strongly head-final language, with heads following both complements and modifiers. Therefore, in the postnominal order CL is widely claimed to be a head that takes NP as its complement (e.g., Murasugi 1991, Kawashima 1998, Watanabe 2006), and the numeral as its specifier (e.g., Watanabe 2006, Huang and Ochi 2011, Ochi 2012), as illustrated in (5). In (4), *-tachi* resides within NP and moves to the specifier of a functional head above the CLP as originally proposed in Watanabe (2006), and further elaborated in Huang and Ochi (2011), Ochi (2012).

The different syntactic analyses do not suggest that the subject at stake is highly debatable or hazardous, but rather complex and that it intrinsically exists in order to explain the mechanisms behind plural suffixes in Japanese. Our endeavor is to show that they express definiteness and that there is a theoretic foundation for their behavior in rendering the nouns they determine definite or indefinite.

According to Huang and Ochi (2011), a functional head such as YP that encodes definiteness/ specificity

is projected above an NP marked with *-tachi*, as shown in (6):

6.

(Ochi 2012: 58)

The NP-*tachi* moves to the specifier of YP for accessibility to a higher head such as *v* for the purpose of case: without moving into an edge of the phrase, it cannot be probed by *v*. As a result of this movement, NP-*tachi* is interpreted as definite. Like Chinese *-men*, *-tachi* is viewed as inducing definiteness (Kurafuji 2004, Ochi 2012), as the contrast in the interpretation between (7a) and (7b) suggests. The sentence in (7b) is not felicitous if the speaker has no particular group of children in mind (Ochi 2012:13)

7. a. Boku-wa kodomo-o sagashiteiru.

I-TOP child-ACC look.for

'I am looking for some/the child(ren).'

- b. Boku-wa kodomo-tachi-o sagashiteiru.

I-TOP child-TACHI-ACC look.for

'I am looking for some specific group of children.'

The existing analyses on Japanese nominal structure suggest that a classifier and the plural marker *-tachi*, regardless of the pre- or postnominal order of the CLP, are not in syntactic complementary distribution: they do not occupy the same syntactic position, and the observed co-occurrence follows from this. In this respect, it means that there are syntactic restrictions at stake with regard to the employment of plural suffixes in Japanese, an observation that aids our demonstration to emphasize that definiteness in Japanese common nouns triggered by plural suffixes is not hazardous, but clearly marked at the semantic and syntactic level. As shown above, the main syntactic operation at stake is movement and turns a common non-definite noun into a pluralized one.

12.3.1. Conclusions to this Section

Even though Number is not overtly expressed in Japanese, this section underlined the possibility of emphasizing plurality with the help of various syntactical schemes like in the case of plural markers (*-tachi*). The comparison with the English plural marker *-s* represents a striking similarity, the reason why we conclude that Number is manifested in Japanese, as well as definiteness, but the methods differ slightly.

We proved earlier that classifiers are an intricate part of Number in Japanese and they act as markers of definiteness. Is the plural marker *-tachi* hazardous or not? The existing analyses on Japanese nominal structure suggest that a classifier and the plural marker *-tachi*, regardless of the pre- or postnominal order of the CLP, are not in syntactic complementary distribution: they do not occupy the same syntactic position, and the

observed co-occurrence follows from this. In this respect, it means that there are syntactic restrictions at stake with regard to the employment of plural suffixes in Japanese, an observation that aids our demonstration to emphasize that definiteness in Japanese common nouns triggered by plural suffixes is not hazardous, but clearly marked at the semantic and syntactic level. As shown above, the main syntactic operation at stake is movement and turns a common non-definite noun into a pluralized one.

Plurality is specified in Num in both English and Japanese. Where the two languages differ is the category on which plurality is realized on the surface. In English, plurality surfaces as *-s* on N. In Japanese, plurality is realized as *-tachi* on N or D. That is, *-tachi* can be attached to D as well as to N. This accounts for the existence of the associative interpretation in Japanese, one argument in favor of *tachi* as a viable plural marker.

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2004, Nakanishi and Ritter 2009). In the case of a proper noun, *Hanako-tachi*, for example, can mean either '*Hanako and others*' (associative) or '*a group of people all named Hanako*' (plural). For common nouns, the usual reading is one of plurality; however, this is not necessarily the case (Nakanishi and Tomioka 2004). The associative reading of the plural marker *-tachi* in Japanese accounts for the colorful peculiarity of this language and argues in favor of novel means to express definiteness, other than those found in European languages.

References

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